

**Indira School of
Business Studies,
Pune**

**All India Council for
Technical Education,
New Delhi**

**National Conference
On
Atmanirbhar Bharat : A Gateway to
Future Growth and Development
Conference Proceedings**

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Our Patrons

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Chairperson
Indira Group of Institutes

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About the Institute

Indira School of Business Studies is one of the forerunner institute under Shree Chanakya Education Society, Pune. Indira School of Business Studies has established its presence in Pune as a premier B- School, offering MBA course affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University. Our MBA course is accredited by National Board of Accreditation, New Delhi. The institute has also featured in top 100 management institutes in India in NIRF ranking published by Ministry of HRD, New Delhi in 2018-19. The institute was established to meet the growing needs of business sector with the explicit vision to provide sustainable impetus to the corporate and entrepreneurial abilities of the students. Our objective of providing 'Management education apt to corporate environment', has been possible due to the sincere and dedicated efforts of the members of ISBS, who have invaluable experience in varied areas like academics, industry, service, and social work. The industry-academia interaction at ISBS brings forth managers of business corporations to extend the knowledge of their challenges, with the future leaders of business. All such efforts are aimed to have an impact commensurate with every student's ambition. The curriculum is ever evolving and has a progressive outlook with an intellectual rigor, where a sound foundation of critical thinking and articulating is laid.

As a driving philosophy, the belief is that the emerging global environment has created a scenario where managers face greater situational challenges, predict, and handle the vagaries of the market and provide sustainable strategic solutions to corporate issues. Such an environment requires professional graduates not only armed with the necessary knowledge but also the confidence of facing extreme competition with greater articulation. The current curriculum design, methodology utilized, including study tours abroad coupled with technology for teaching, keeps the students abreast of the trends in the field of business management.

About Conference

Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyaan (Self-reliant India) campaign is the vision of new India visualized by the Hon'ble Prime Minister of India Shri Narendra Modi. On 12 May 2020, our PM raised a clarion call to the nation giving a kick start to the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyaan and set the goal of a self-reliant India. It will be achieved with the help of collaborative, innovative and transformative policies of the Government. The aim is to make the country and its citizens independent and self-reliant in all senses. The five pillars of Atmanirbhar Bharat are - Economy, Infrastructure, System, Vibrant Demography and Demand. As part of the Atmanirbhar Bharat package, numerous government decisions took place such as changing the definition of MSMEs, boosting scope for private participation in numerous sectors, increasing FDI in the defence sector, and the vision has found support in many sectors such as the solar manufacturing sector. The government took several bold reforms such as Supply Chain Reforms for Agriculture, Rational Tax Systems, Simple & Clear Laws, Capable Human Resource and Strong Financial System. It is necessary to discuss the present status of these initiatives and their impact on the Indian economy in terms of employment, income generation, technology development etc.

In the above context, ISBS aims to provide an opportunity to academicians, researchers, industry practitioners and students to discuss and share contemporary aspects revolving around Atmanirbhar Bharat-A gateway to Future Growth and Development of India.

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Title: A Study of Awareness about Women Entrepreneurship Scheme

Authors

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Abstract

Women Entrepreneurs means the women or a group of women who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. An increasing number of startups and new businesses have been seen in India over the last decade, the majority of them by men. While many Indian women have entrepreneurial ambitions, it is often more difficult for them to succeed. This paper will discuss why women are not able to build their own start-ups. The primary reason behind low female entrepreneurship rates is women are not aware of schemes available for them to start their own venture and also they lack in training required for starting the venture. It is recommended through the study that women entrepreneurs start businesses with adequate funds through schemes and also find new markets and consult with professionals. Most importantly, the policies, programs, and schemes related to the development of women's entrepreneurship should be available readily, should spread awareness about it at a larger scale implemented honestly. The study is the first prominent investigation of the relation between the schemes available and barriers faced by women entrepreneurs. The paper offers a set of recommendations that can help push women's entrepreneurial empowerment in rural area.

Keywords

Women entrepreneurship, Self-reliant, Socio-cultural beliefs, Rural challenges, Awareness

Title: Display Marketing on Online Media Platform and its effects on Consumer Behavior.

Authors

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Abstract

This paper summarizes the display advertising literature, organizing the content by the agents in the display advertising ecosystem, and proposes new research directions. In doing so, we take an

interdisciplinary view, drawing connections among diverse streams of theoretical and empirical research in information systems, marketing, economics, operations, and computer science. By providing an integrated view of the display advertising ecosystem, we hope to bring attention to the outstanding research opportunities in this economically consequential and rapidly growing market.

Keywords:

Display Advertising, Online Platform, Literature Review, Real-Time Data

**Title: A Comparative study of Consumer perception toward Chinese
and Indian Electronic Items**

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Abstract

Atmanirbhar Bharat focuses on making our country self-reliant. Thus, the government is promoting various businesses to come up with innovative products and services. Due to government policies small and medium enterprise may witness very favourable environment. In few years Indian small and medium organization may come up with very good electronic products and which may become a competitive alternative to foreign electronic brands which are currently dominating the market. However, it is very important to investigate if consumers are willing to buy indigenous electronic products! It is really important for Indian companies to understand their perception in the minds of consumers compared to foreign (Chinese) electronic products. The current study will focus on willingness of Consumers to switch their brands of electronic products to Indian Made electronic product. The current electronic market is being dominated by foreign brands particularly Chinese products. So, it will be useful for Indian organizations to know willingness of consumers to buy Indian electronic products compared to Chinese products which currently are more economical and a step ahead in quality.

Key Words - Atamanirbhar Bharat Campaign, Decorative lights, consumer animosity

**Title: Empirical Investigation of Technology Acceptance Model towards
Digital Wearable Devices**

Authors

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Abstract

As demonstrated in the theory of reasoned Action, the Technology Acceptance Model postulates that the use of an information system is determined by the behavioral intention, but on the other hand, that the behavioral intention is determined by the person's attitude towards the use of the system and also by his perception of its utility. According to Davis, the attitude of an individual is not the only factor that determines his use of a system, but is also based on the impact which it may have on his performance. Therefore, even if an employee does not welcome an information system, the probability that he will use it is high if he perceives that the system will improve his performance at work. Besides, the Technology Acceptance Model hypothesizes a direct link between perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. With two systems offering the same features, a user will find more useful the one that he finds easier to use.

Key words - Technology, Model, Behavioral etc

Title: Requirement for Skill Development and Vocational Education to become Atmanirbhar

Author

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Abstract

As VUCA world becomes more pervasive, what does that indicate for future of work? We are entering in a world that is predominantly shaped by man-machine collaboration, and hence this becomes right time to forecast and start honing skills that will reshape businesses and industries. Are we capable to embrace real power of Artificial Intelligence, and Machine Learning and build a successful career for workforce of future? Will only digital skills give us competitive edge or human skills remain pertinent

in digital future of work? What about competencies like building sustainable culture in organizations, making them more agile, empathetic, and having an environment of Trust and Connected Leadership? In future, both human skills and technology together, shall help us meet challenges and embrace the changes. One of the reports published by World Economic Forum on Future of Jobs, highlighted the need to rely-on self-management and critical thinking skills, to reap benefits of increase in automation, and create jobs that take advantage of both automation and human creativity & adaptability. This report of WEF also mentioned that 43% of businesses indicated that they might decrease their workforce (which may become redundant) due to technology integration, and shall move towards automation. A recent IMF analysis indicates that approximately 15% of workforce across 35 countries may face redundancy ahead. This paper attempts to delve on some of the questions raised here, and deep dive to find skills that may become redundant, and ones, which shall come to foray.

Keywords: VUCA, Future Skills, Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning, Empathy & agility, Connected Leadership

Title : Entrepreneurship and COVID-19 – Current Challenges and Future Opportunities

Authors

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Abstract

A pandemic like COVID-19 has adverse effects on the economy and development of businesses. However, innovators and entrepreneurs who think outside the box can help develop the technologies and solutions that will have a lasting and positive impact in the post-pandemic climate. Beyond the humanitarian tragedy of the COVID-19 pandemic, the virus is also having a growing impact on local economies and the global economy. Policies that reduce barriers to entrepreneurship, provide incentives for start-ups, and boost entrepreneurial potential could help speed up the recovery and

preserve aggregate employment in the long term. Strategic agility is critical for business enterprises and organizations to deal successfully with this grand societal challenge of COVID-19. Competences, acquired through various forms of nonformal and even more formal training, will be an important asset and opportunity for those young people who will develop and acquire them, and who are willing and able to practice them through their agile entrepreneurial and project-related creativity.

Keywords

Entrepreneurship, COVID-19, Start-ups, women entrepreneurs, social entrepreneur

Title : Study of costing aspects of Renewable Energy

Authors

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Abstract

On a Levelized-cost premise, sunlight-based and wind power are presently cutthroat with Renewable Energy. In any case, the supply of these sustainable assets is variable and irregular, not at all like customary force plants. Therefore, the expense of utilizing level retail evaluating rather than dynamic, minimal expense estimating—since quite a while ago pushed by market analysts—will develop. We assess the possible increases from dynamic estimating in high-sustainable frameworks utilizing an original model of force organic market. The model kicks off something new in incorporating interest in age and capacity limit with the ordered activity of the framework, including a record of stores, and interest framework with various interhour flexibilities for various utilizations, and replacement among power and different labor and products. The model is open source and completely versatile to different settings. Steady with prior investigations, we track down that unique estimating gives a minimal social advantage in Renewable energy ruled force frameworks.

Keywords : Energy, Renewable Energy, Green Energy, Geo-Thermal Energy, Clean Energy, Sustainable, Electricity, Fossil Fuels, Technology, Non-Renewable Energy, Solar Energy

**Title : Case-Based Research on Enhancing Student Awareness of Sustainable
Development Goals in B-Schools**

Authors

Dr. Renu Bhargava, Dr. Kalpana Deshmukh

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to see how well management education can regularly enhance student awareness of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). The idea is that Management Education may be tailored to create the talents and mindsets of future corporate value providers. The paper builds its case based on the referenced material published in Responsible Management Education, Some Voices From Asia, Author: Renu Bhargava, Business Expert Press Publication, 2017, New York. The objective of the current paper is first, to portray to the readers the concept entailing Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) as perceived by the United Nations Global Compact and the emergent Principles of Responsible Management Education (PRME). Secondly to show case the relevance for immersion of PRME as an eco-system in the genre of business school education and to consistently support its tenets while imparting learning to students of business management. This case discusses possible approaches for business schools regarding the way education can be modulated and sustained for students to become responsible for generating sustainable value for business and society at large and to work for an inclusive and sustainable global economy in their professional lives. Using the information provided by United Nations Global Compact and the emergent Principles of Management Education (PRME) this paper provides a summary of efforts made by the said business school to institutionalize PRME. The excerpts in this paper and the historical perspective are stated according to real time information as published in Responsible Management Education, Some Voices From Asia.

Keywords : Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), Responsible Management Education (RME), Sustainability, Outcome Based Learning (OBL), Course Level Objectives, and Program Level Objectives.

Title : Institutional Sales: Managing Customers for Sales Not Profit

Authors

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Abstract:

Concept of Institutional Sales is not new in the industry. Various Organizations who are having chain stores across a city, state or even a country end up purchasing the products from a centralized purchase store commonly termed as Institutional Purchase store. There are benefits of institutional purchase to the organization and also to the company who is selling these products as they end up clearing their inventory and are better prepared when it comes to facing competition. However, there are certain cases where the concept of Institutional sales has ended up doing more harm than good to the seller company. This case study will help companies in understanding the cons of Institutional Selling and help them in providing a road map for framing policies with respect to Institutional Sales.

Keywords: Institutional Sales, Business Ethics, Sales Management

Title : Make in India: New Paradigm for Socio-Economic growth in India

Authors

Dr. Vikas Barbate

Prof. Pavandeep Singh Duggal

Abstract

Indian economy is dominated by the service sector. If India were to improve its socio-economic growth, it is amply clear that the focus should be on industry or manufacturing sector. With this objective in view, India in 2014 launched its ambitious Make in India program. In order to achieve its objectives, the program focused on four pillars – new processes, new infrastructure, new sectors and new mindset. This study was meant to achieve three objectives - to study the growth in FDI Inflows; to study the growth in exports; and to study the improvement in Ease of Doing Business ranking. The hypotheses were tested using secondary data from sources such as RBI, DPIIT and other secondary sources. The

conclusions of this study are – first, there is significant growth in the FDI inflows for India, second, the growth in exports is not significant and third, there is significant improvement in ease of doing business rankings. The credit of FDI inflow growth coupled with significant improvement in the ease of doing business rankings goes to the Make in India program. These findings are clearly indicator of the program's success. The limitation of this study is that it is restricted to evidence of 5-6 years only. Moreover, it uses data for the all the sectors on a combined basis.

Keywords: FDI, exports, ease of doing business, manufacturing, delicensing

**Title : A Consumer Perception, Purchase Behavior and Purchase Intention of
Organic Food Among Working Class People**

Authors

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Abstract

The current study focuses on understanding the factors, personal attitude, and perceived behaviour control that influence consumer behaviour and health consciousness as an additional factor. It further explains the role of knowledge as a moderating variable in organic food purchase intention. This approach treats food as a basic health necessity but does not ignore the esthetic dimensions of food intake (beauty) or the hedonistic (pleasurable). This phenomenon, which has contributed to news and change in these fields, of how people eat spans many facets of the social and cultural environment, including business practices and media coverage of terms of food. Attitudes towards organic food consumption and consideration have changed internationally, influencing, but also integrating, local food and conventional gastronomy crops. The environmentally friendly solution has been to establish and to inflict major losses to local habitats, wildlife, wetlands, potable water resources, and even the health and productivity of farmers worldwide, as well as over-producing and using pesticides in traditional agriculture. Because of its shortcomings in food system transformation, however, the effects of organic agriculture are unclear for their extent of environmental benefits. Reducing food waste and dietary changes in some situations may give greater benefits. Many factors have led to the increasing

popularity of organic food products. The reasons why organic products are better than conv-produced, health and nutrition concerns, environmental concerns, the issue of using traditional agriculture chemicals as well as pesticides, the loss of factory trust, and animal welfare issues.

Title : Is India ready to embrace electronic vehicle?

Authors

Prof. Geetika Jha

Mr. Manthan Ghadole, Ms. Sakshi Raghuvanshi,

Dr. D. Y. Patil Business School, Pune

Abstract:

Deteriorating climate change is the major concern of the economies across the globe. In such a scenario electric vehicle is being considered as the possible substitute to the environment and the industry. In spite of governments implementing many electric vehicles (EV) policies the current market share of the EV is low relatively. This paper aims at studying the consumer preference and demand of the EV that helps in understanding the customer perception towards buying the EV in India. The potential scope of the electric automobile and the consumer viewpoint for these vehicles in India is analysed in this paper. Data Analysis and Interpretation is done by using the data sampling process using the sample size of 106 participants. In this survey we found that maximum participants are willing to opt for electric/hybrid vehicles, and also in favour to use various government schemes.

Keywords: Electric vehicles, Consumer Viewpoint, Environment, Consumer potential, Market trends, Government scheme, Government Policy.

Title : The Role of Entrepreneurial Self Efficacy in Business Management Students'

Entrepreneurial Venture Motive

Author

Dr. Mrityunjay Kumar

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Abstract

The Paper is influenced by Atmanirbhar Bharat idea and it studied the Self Efficacy in context of Gender and focused on Business Management Students. Entrepreneurial self-efficacy is a construct

that measures a person's conviction in their abilities to execute on the various skill requirements necessary to pursue a replacement venture opportunity. Objectives of this paper are based on Entrepreneurial skills and self-efficacy. For that data collected from 100 students from Navi Mumbai. For data analysis ANOVA, Post Hoc Test and M-U test have been done through SPSS. Result shows for new venture there should be set of skills and gender is significant to self-efficacy.

This research paper opens the area of further research.

Keywords: Self Efficacy, Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial Skills, Gender, Business Management, Atmanirbhar Bharat

Title : Role of HRM in AtmaNirbhar Bharat

Authors

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Abstract

All industries across the globe are going through challenging times because of the Covid-19 pandemic. Many organisations have initiated for scenario planning and are taking the required operational responses to ensure business continuity post-COVID-19. In this situation, there are a lot of issues faced by organisations in acquiring talents and managing human resources. Human Resource Management (HRM) functions are a vital part to the smooth operations in any organization. Every organisation is evolving in nature, hence for improving performance and productivity, change is inevitable. This study addresses the various issues faced at managing human resources in the post Covid-19 period. The descriptive study also analyses the changing role of human resource during these changing times and conclude with the possible strategies for better management of human resources.

Keywords: Human resource, Post-Covid, Employees, Pandemic, Performance

Title : The Role of Labour Laws in Atma Nirbhar Bharat

Authors

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Abstract

The labour laws of any country are very critical in its economic and overall development. They have a critical role in implementing the ease of doing business types of policies. This paper is an attempt to compare the Indian labour law framework with some developed / developing countries' labour law framework, with reference to learn how we can modify and update our labour laws, to enable them to contribute to the AtmaNirbhar Bharat. The paper will seek to offer some insights as to what are good or positive aspects of our existing labour law framework, and which aspects may need modification and improvement, with reference to making India (Bharat) an AtmaNirbhar country.

Keywords : Labour Laws, Ease of Doing Business, Atma Nirbhar Bharat

Title : Women entrepreneurship as second inning career: A need for Atmanirbhar Bharat

Authors

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Abstract

Entrepreneurs is the person who sets up, organise and runs a business enterprise. Entrepreneur plays very important role in physical and mental architecture of any organisation how entrepreneur tries to build rapport with employees, creates impact on sustainability of organisation. In today's world, with a lot of dynamism, organisations need a strong person who can take up the entire responsibility of organisation. With many factors affecting onto employment of women, this paper tries to highlight

about women second inning at career along with women entrepreneurship. To make India as Atmanirbhar, we need to promote women entrepreneurs. The objective of this research paper is to understand the factors affecting on women Entrepreneurs during their second inning at career. It also highlights about the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs during their second inning. In nutshell we can conclude by saying, women entrepreneur faces many challenges, and many factors affect women Entrepreneurship. Social structure affected them most. Self-doubt and low confidence affected ability to take decisions which in a way has also affected their risk-taking ability. Support of family members act as source of motivation, without their support it was difficult and challenging to manage the entire show. Author has tried to give suitable recommendation to overcome the challenges anticipated.

Keywords : Women entrepreneurs, Career, Second Inning, Atmanirbhar Bharat

Title : Role Of Women Entrepreneurship In Self Reliant India

Author

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Abstract

The arc of India's evolution had left behind an important demographic: women. Despite advancements in social criteria, India's prosperity has not translated to women's economic presence and growth. Women's entrepreneurship was once a disregarded subject, but as education and awareness have grown among women, the situation has changed, and women have emerged as today's most outstanding and motivating entrepreneurs. Women's increasing presence as entrepreneurs has resulted in a shift in the demographics of business and economic success in the country. Women-owned enterprises are playing an increasingly important role in society, encouraging others and creating additional job opportunities. Economic empowerment of women is the most effective way for integrating women into Atmanirbhar Bharat's developmental goals. Women's entrepreneurship is an important aspect to make India self-reliant. It not only benefits the economy by creating jobs, but also benefits women in terms of social and personal transformation. When we talk about "Women Entrepreneurship," we're talking about a type of business ownership and creation that empowers women economically and improves their social

standing. This paper explains the significance of women entrepreneurship, challenges faced by women Entrepreneurs, and focuses on the role of women entrepreneurs in the India economy and their contributions to make India self-reliant.

Keywords : Women Entrepreneurship, Women Entrepreneurs, Indian Economy, Self-reliant India

Title : Social Entrepreneurs As Social Change Agents

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ABSTRACT

Social entrepreneurship has become an emerging topic of discussion in India and around the world. People have found this concept of humanity a bit fascinating in nature. It has the best blend of social service and entrepreneurship; this amalgamation makes it most attractive and exclusive in nature. Usually entrepreneurship is associated to commercial activities and being cruelly profit making and overlooking social benefits or societal well-being. In the present time of substantial industrialization and economic growth, societal gains have been ignored in India and all around the world. With the concept of social entrepreneurship intensifying in India and around the world has helped in serving the society in better way. The share of social entrepreneurs in sustainable economic improvement is being progressively recognized and various steps are being taken by States, government, NGOs and social enterprises to promote social entrepreneurship to bring a composed social change in the society.

Different sectors such as government, business institutions, social enterprises and social entrepreneurs are coming forward for a united and synchronized approach for the expansion of social entrepreneurship. Social enterprises act as a dynamic promoter for bringing social change and innovation and to raise the recent status of people towards progress. This paper explains the concept of social entrepreneurs as change agent.

Keywords : Social Entrepreneurship, Societal needs, Social Entrepreneurs, Social change

Title: Cost Reduction of Catalyst of PEMFC for Promotion of Electric Car Industry

Authors

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Abstract

This paper proposes application of improvised renewable energy source for popularising electric cars in India to kick start Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyaan and set a goal of self-reliant India. The advantages of Electric cars are well-known to everybody as an alternative to costly fuel of petrol or gas, reduction of air pollution by avoiding burning of the same and controlling the global warming affecting the human life. At present three types of batteries are available in the market for electric cars, but they are having their own limitations for transforming / promoting the car industry. Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) is currently the most promising type of fuel cell for Electric Vehicles. This uses electrolyte which composes solid polymer film and acidified Teflon to allow Hydrogen ions conduction from Anode to Cathode. The use of solid dry electrolyte eliminates liquid handling problems associated with other types of fuel cells which are using liquefied electrolyte as well as its replenishment problems. PEMFC works around 100 °C with pressure of 1 to 2 bar, good enough to simplify safety issues, material issues as well as quick start-up problems with desirable low temperature operations and still achieve thermodynamic efficiency above 80%. The operating potential of cell is in the range of 0.5 to 1.1 Volts DC. PEMFC is promising fuel cell for moderate power applications including LCV owing to its higher voltage, current and power densities at low pressure of fuel with compact and rugged structure. The main advantage of PEMFC is green energy generation giving water and heat as by-products, while Hydrogen is a higher energy density fuel giving 2e- per molecule. But the main disadvantage of PEMFC is use of costly Platinum as a catalyst and expensive Membrane. Another key problem of the direct hydrogen PEMFC system is the hydrogen storage tank. This can be solved by a range of hydrogen storage methods like compressed hydrogen storage, liquid hydrogen storage,

Hydrogen storage in metal hydrides and chemical storage of hydrogen in cartridges but at the cost of energy density, efficiency, cost, weight and volume. Reducing weight and volume to match power density is an important challenge in Electric Vehicles. PEMFC utilising methanol-water mixture with reformer seems to be cumbersome as far as its application to Electric Vehicles is concerned. In direct-methanol fuel cell (DM-PEMFC), use of reformer can be eliminated but with reduced potential of 0.25 to 0.4 Volts with reduced power density of 40 to 100mw/cm². Such low voltage is due to cross over of methanol from anode to cathode. This system requires 10 times platinum loading (additional 5mg/cm²) than direct hydrogen PEMFC. Higher concentrated methanol enhances the cross over problem. Despite these challenges DM-PEMFC can give 1W to 1KW of power capacity suitable for low power electronic applications and electric two wheelers. Hence, this paper proposes use of Hydrogen fuel cell only with modification in catalyst by using nano particles of transition elements to minimise platinum so that PEMFC becomes a good and lucrative choice for Electric Vehicles.

Keywords : PEMFC, DM-PEMFC, Atmanirbhar, Bharat, Abhiyaan, Membrane, Fuel Cell, EV, Electric car, platinum, nano, transition elements

Title : Investor's Perception towards Banking Sector in Stock market

Authors

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Ms. Anushree Satpute

Mr. Gourav Sharma

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune

Abstract

This paper is an attempt to study financial backer's perception towards banking area in Stock market. There are distinctive individual with alternate point of view in which stock they feel less danger and exceptional yield. This paper leads a poll and tracks down the different parts of the financial backer's attitude towards the financial area of the securities exchange. Banking area is the foundation of the economy which additionally goes through its own periods of high points and low points. When everything in the economy is blushing, loaning and borrowings blast and this thus prompts sound development in banks. The study was done by surveying 100 respondents who are active investors. The

study has revealed that majority of the investors invest in the stocks of banking sector. Thus, it can be concluded that investors who expect high return is ready to take high risk by investing in banking stocks and bank nifty.

Keywords: Banks, Financial, Investors' perception, Financial backers, RBI.

Title : Opportunities and Challenges for self-reliant India in Marketing

Author

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Abstract

Ever since the COVID-19 pandemic began in March 2020, the world's economy has been in tatters due to the resulting health and economic shocks. To deal with the pandemic, countries around the world imposed strict lockdowns on the movement of people, on international travel, and on the transportation of goods and services to minimize the threat to health and safety. This has resulted in many industries and organizations either being shut down or operating at minimum capacity, and the effects are visible globally. To address the economic challenge, on 12th May India's Prime Minister, in his AtmaNirbhar Bharat Abhiyan (Self-reliant India Campaign), announced an overall economic package worth rupees 20 lakh crore (US\$280 billion), 10% of India's GDP, with emphasis on making India as a self-reliant nation. This paper analyses the role of start-up initiatives and innovative projects in building a self-reliant India. The study further assesses how this mission can help the micro, small and medium enterprises (MSME) in establishing their business. It also provides a few caselets of successful start-ups in India.

Keywords: AtmaNirbhar Bharat, Entrepreneurship, Innovation, Self-reliant India, Covid-19

Title : Review Of Economic Measures Enacted During Recent Pandemic To Curb The Financial Distress In India

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Abstract

The current pandemic caused by the spread coronavirus has been negatively affecting the economy of many countries. This included developing as well as some highly developed nations. It was quite a concern for the governments to assess how this pandemic would hurt the economy and to predict the severity of the damage it could cause to various strata's in the society. But it was imperative to draw out some strategies which can curb this devastation and control the distress it can further cause. It was more critical for countries like India to think about robust financial assistance to be provided to various sector considering the scarcity of economic resources we hold. Hence, with this research paper the authors have expressed the review of such economic measures enacted during recent pandemic to curb the financial distress in India.

Keywords: Economic Measures, Financial Distress, Pandemic

Top 3 Trends in Wealth Management Industry

Authors

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Abstract :

Wealth Management industry is extremely competitive and customers are highly demanding, as their needs constantly evolve. The global health crisis 'Covid-19 pandemic' caused massive disruption and service delivery disconnect across the industry and the way they use to function and carry out their day

today routine business. The pandemic with challenges brought array of opportunity which are clearly visible from the latest trends in the wealth management industry. To capitalize on the market opportunity, Wealth Management firms needs to remain in pace with current trends like rapid digitization and opportunities with the use of emerging technology, demand for sustainable investment offerings.

Keywords : Wealth management Trends, Mutual Fund, Sustainable investment, ESG, Digitization

Title: Role of SHG and cottage industry in empowerment of women through e-commerce platform

Authors

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Abstract :

Purpose – The purpose of this paper is to understand the role of the SHG/ Cottage industry in the empowerment of women as well as the role of the government in fostering entrepreneurship among women. The study attempts to extend the behavior of the government by considering various schemes launched under Atmanirbhar Bharat and the role of E-Commerce platform

Design/Methodology/Approach – Data was collected from 20 respondents from various SHGs from the Mumbai region and 60 women working in those SHGs. The structured questionnaire was used for collecting data and the tool used for analyzing data was Pie graphs and tables

Findings - In the study, it was found that 40% of the SHGs/Cottage industry have given importance to the railway to market their product and half of the SHGs and cottage industry agreed on empowerment of women through an e-commerce platform. While many families dominate women and do not allow the women to step out for work.

Practical implications- This research will help to understand the awareness of government schemes among SHGs/Cottage industry and what steps needs to be taken by the SHGs to avail those facilities for empowering women.

Keywords : Empowerment, SHGs, Cottage Industry, Atmanirbhar entrepreneurship schemes, E-commerce Platform

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